

NESTORE

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D1.2 NESTORE website

HOW TO COMMUNICATE THE PROJECT ON THE WEB

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www.nestore-coach.eu

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RESPONSIBLE PARTNER:	NEOS
CONTRIBUTORS:	Sandro Repetti (NEOS), Estelle Huchet (AGE), Gabriela Candea (ROPARDO)
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Approvals

DATE	NAME	ORGANIZATION	ROLE
2018.01.30	Cinzia Mambretti	POLIMI	Reviewer
2018.01.31	Estelle Huchet	AGE	WP Leader
2018.01.31	Giuseppe Andreoni	POLIMI	Scientific Coordinator

Short Abstract

This document describes the aims and the development of the NESTORE Project public website:
www.nestore-coach.eu

Key Words

Website

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1. General assumptions and background

The website (www.nestore-coach.eu) was technically developed by ROPARDO following a design by NEOS and with the support of all project partners in terms of content provision and review.

The content of the website will become richer as the project moves forward with news being regularly posted and main pages being updated with project work progress and results.

The long-term objective of the website is to create a community of interested parties around the project to:

- accelerate their involvement,
- create awareness of the results, and
- inform them about the latest evolutions in the field.

2. Concept

The NESTORE website aims to serve both scientific and lay audiences with content addressed to both targets. The concept thus aims to present the project to different categories of users interested in the project following a user-specific content architecture. In order to do so, the architecture was designed based on several users' profiles that have eventually been grouped under four categories for the sake of clarity on the home page: Older Persons, Healthcare Professionals, IT Professionals and Policy Makers.

Figure 1 - NESTORE Website Home Page

3. Style

The design of the websites derives directly from the concept of the project logo and the project visual identity, as described in D1.4 – Dissemination Plan:

Figure 2 - NESTORE Vertical Logo

For images, human presence has been preferred to abstractive composition or drawings.

Figure 3 - NESTORE Home Page Detail

4. Accessibility and esclusiveness

Careful considerations have been given to gender-sensitive aspects of the whole website, including the images that have been selected for usage on the website. In the illustration of the news and additional pages that will be developed over the course of the project, more images will populate the website and thus diversifying the gender and ethical backgrounds of profiles depicted on the website.

5. Architecture

The NESTORE website aims to give an overview about the main information and goals of the project, with a focus over the project overall approach, the Technology that are going to be developed and the resources produced by the project; it finally gives the opportunity to get in touch with the project participants.

Figure 4 - NESTORE Techonology Webpage

The table below gives an overview of what will be the final architecture of the project website. It should be noted that given the preliminary stage NESTORE is currently in, some pages remain invisible until they can be fed with consistent content. It is the case of: the sub-section of the "Technology" section, the "Use Cases" and the "Resources" sections as well as their sub-pages.

Figure 5 - Representation of NESTORE Website Content

Legend:

- Coloured boxes: pages that will be online for the website release on January 31st, 2018
- Black boxes: pages that will be released once the project will move forward and develop content

6. Management

The website will be updated consistently over the course of the NESTORE project tracking the story and reporting updates about the general activities, news, participation to events as well as the results of the Pilots, the design of the NESTORE solutions, the technology development, the experiences of the users and the outcome of the scientific research.

